

Effect of Occupational Stress on Teachers of Self Finance Colleges in Varanasi District

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Abstract:-In today's changing world every individual is facing a certain level of stress and none of the profession is even stress free. Every one facing stress within the family and relatives, business, study work, or any of socio-economic activity they are involved in. Stress has become the part and problem of everyone's life, it became the main concern to everyone, and apart from that everybody wants a stress-free life. Teaching profession are generally viewed as a low stress profession and characterized as light workload, flexibility in working hours and benefits such as health facility, foreign trips for conference etc. However, recent studies suggested that the teachers of self finance colleges are facing a high level of occupational stress due to avoidance of rules made by authorities and concentration of college administrative power in single hand. This concentration of power and high level of profit maximization desire leads to exploitation of employees of college. So, this study is conducted in five self finance colleges of Varanasi District and total thirty two respondents have been taken to collect the data from teachers of different demographical factors and different courses. Percentage method has been used to analyse the data. The study reveals the prevalence of high level of stress among teachers of self finance colleges in Varanasi District. This paper also recommends various measures that can be adopted by the institution and authorities to reduce the stress among teachers.

Keywords: *Occupational Stress, Self-finance Colleges, Job insecurity, Career development*

Introduction

Stress is the term used to describe the feelings of tension / exhaustion generally associated with work overload. Stress is natural phenomenon in the daily life of persons. It refers to the strain between conflict of us and our external environment, leading to emotional and physical pressure. It is not possible to live without stress in this changing world, whether he or she is a student or working men and women. There is negative and positive stress, both depending upon individual's perception of the tension in between the two forces. The stress bears effects on both the employer and employees. The word stress as per the Oxford Dictionary as "a state of affairs involving demand on physical or mental energy". In medical vernacular stress is defined as anxiety of body's homeostasis. Human health is detrimental to extreme stress. An occupational stress may be caused by various factors such as excessive work load, time pressure, fatigue from physical strains, travelling and in coping up with changes in work.

At workplace, it can help to enhance an individual's moral, satisfaction, performance and personal achievement. We can say that, stress is impact of any pressure that exceeds one's capacity to stabilize oneself physiologically, psychologically or emotionally. The levels of stress tolerance in some people are very high and they face various stressors in the environment in very easy way, whereas some peoples unable to perform well in stress condition only except the level of stress that energizes them to do their best efforts (Sekaran, 2004). This shows that it depends upon individual to interpret the stressors as Eustress, while other experience Distress. These effects may last long time or be short term and diminish quickly (Newstrom, 2007).

TEACHER AND TEACHERS STRESS

A teacher is a person who imparts knowledge to the community of students'. The teachers play an important role in giving formal education right from schools, colleges and in universities. The teachers of non aided, self funded college affiliated to a government university following its syllabus and curriculum is known as self financing college faculty. Williams and Gersch (2004) concluded that pressure of regular inspection and excessive work load were perceived to cause high level of stress in teachers. Ultimately, students are the pillars of future of the nation and the teachers are the foundation of social building and future of entire country. So, they must be free from all type of stress.

An occupational stress is any force that affects the stability of an individual beyond its limit to bear physical and psychological strain. Working in an organisation does not provide only income but also exerts huge pressures on them with respect to performance of duty in poor organisational climate. This ultimately have negative outcome in achieving the organisational and individual goals. Thus, the job environment is a big source of socio-psychological stress, which has negative effects on the well-being of the teachers. Workplace stress has huge effect on the people's behaviour, which affect the efficiency of individual and organisation. Occupational stress can easily be described as the condition where job related factors disrupt / improve the psychological or physiological condition of employees.

Literature Review

Ryhal and Singh (1996) studied the correlation of job stress among faculty of university. Their study revealed that asst. professors experienced more job stress than associate professors and professors. So, the lower strata have high level of occupational stress.

Potter et al. (2002) found that at work place interpersonal stressors have the great influence on the employees. Even interpersonal conflicts prevailing at the work place sometime cause diseases and health declines. So, results proved that socio-psychological environment of workplace have high level effects on employee.

Kaur, Ravinder (1997) has gone through a study on socio- psycho problems of female teachers working in colleges and schools of Punjab. The paper is the study of the socio- psycho problems of female teachers with respect to institution. Policymakers, Administrators should help to create a suitable working environment that promotes fairness and conveys caring. If teachers feel that the organisational climate supports in balancing family and work responsibilities, they may experience high levels of work and family enrichment and satisfaction as well. Family support to organizational policies may be made to provide assistance to teachers coping with socio- psycho problems.

Adnan Iqbal & Husam Kokash (2011) in this study they focused on the perception of Teaching Faculty towards occupational stress. They found that the management and administration should always focus on stress of Teaching Faculty. Teaching like other professions has become a stressful profession (Hepburn & Brown, 2001; Johnson et. al., 2005) as teachers have to take multiple responsibilities keeping in mind the deadlines.

Larson (1977) found in his study, that the post of elementary school principals having a huge work overload in respect of students discipline report, staff appraisal and expression. Moreover, the post of principals has role ambiguity in respect of curriculum and instruction and also great amount of stress in respect of social support, participation & utilization of individuals' abilities.

Sharron S. K. Leung in his study examined occupational stress and mental health among secondary school teachers in Hong Kong, and found that teachers in Hong Kong have high level of occupational stress and low level

of stress coping resources. Cognitive- behavioral programs are recommended to enhance teachers' stress management.

Objectives of the study

1. To investigate various factors causing Occupational Stress among teachers of self finance colleges.
2. To know the steps taken by the college administration to manage the stress among teachers.
3. To study the impact of stress on the social and family life of teachers.

Scope of the Study

This study has been conducted in five private self- finance college of Varanasi District. The main focus of the study is to cover the impact of various factors responsible for causing the stress among the teachers of self finance colleges and the measures taken by the college to cope up with these factors of stress. This study is to extend the information related with the condition of teachers in private higher educational institutions, which further laid down the policymakers for making policy thereof.

Limitation of the Study

1. College curtailment to collect the information from faculties that is why the no. of respondents is limited.
2. Faculties were giving short time to give response due to classes and other academic and corporate responsibilities.
3. Respondents were much hesitating in giving the answers of many questions.
4. College name is kept confidential as per the demand of respondents on the condition of which they have given the response.

Research Methodology

The survey was carried out to analyse the factors causing stress among the teachers of self finance colleges'. The data has been collected through primary as well secondary source. The primary data collected through faculties of five self finance college of Varanasi District and secondary data through various previous researches, magazines, newspapers and e-material etc. To ensure the more purposeful outcome of the research the selection of college and respondent was done in such a way that can represent the condition of self finance teachers of colleges, with various attributes such as UG and PG teachers, subject differentiation (art, science, commerce and law) or male and female teachers etc. The universe of the study is Varanasi District with sample unit of self finance teachers and sample size of 32 respondents. Data analysis has been done through percentage of all the aspect of questionnaire (with few open ended questions) and personal interview and presented by table and chart.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1. Demographic Study of teachers of self finance colleges

Particulars	Respondents	Percentage
Age of the respondent		
20-29 Years	13	40.62
30 -39 Years	15	46.88
40 -49 Years	4	12.5
Above 50 Years	0	0
Total	32	100
Gender of the respondents		
Male	19	59.37
Female	13	40.63
Total	32	100
Type of family		

Nuclear	12	37.50
Joint	20	62.50
Total	32	100
Location of college		
Rural area	21	65.62
Urban area	11	34.38
Total	32	100
Monthly Income		
Less than Rs. 10000	12	37.50
Rs. 10001 - Rs. 20000	17	53.12
Rs. 20001 – Rs 30000	3	9.38
Rs. 30001 – Rs 40000	0	0
More than Rs. 40000	0	0
Total	32	100

Table 2. Job insecurity is the significant cause of stress among teachers

S.N.	Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Yes	25	78.12
2.	No	5	15.63
3.	Can't say	2	6.25
	Total	32	100

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: Above data reveal that 78.12% teachers felt that job insecurity is the significant cause of stress in a self finance college whereas 15.23% teachers denied any relation between job insecurity and stress, followed by 6.25% were not able to say anything regarding above statement.

Table 3. Poor opportunities for research & career growth and development

S.N.	Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Yes	20	62.50
2.	No	9	28.13
3.	Can't say	3	9.38
	Total	32	100

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: Above table show that 62.50% of teachers of self finance colleges have very poor opportunities in respect of research and career growth & development where as 28.13% feels that the opportunity to the teachers in respect of the research and career growth & development is abundant and 9.38% were not given any one sided remark on above statement.

Table 4. Research and Academic activities performed

S.N.	Research and Academic activities performed	Permitted	Percentage (Out of Total 32 respondents)	Not Permitted	Percentage (Out of Total 32 respondents)
1.	Attending Orientation & Refresher	03	9.38	29	90.62
2.	Research Project (Minor/Major)	00	0.00	32	100

3.	To attend outstation Conferences and Seminar	05	15.62	27	84.38
4.	Participation in Vivo- Voce of students	02	6.25	30	93.75
5.	Guiding Ph.D scholar	00	0.00	32	100
6.	Delivered Guest lecturer in other institutions	04	12.50	28	87.50
7.	Leave for pursuing Ph.D	02	6.25	30	93.75

Interpretation: A clear cut demarcation is shown from the above table that research and academic activities are barely or not permitted to the teachers of self finance college.

Table 5. Excessive additional workload

S.N.	Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
8.	Yes	19	59.37
9.	No	10	31.25
10.	Can't say	3	9.38
	Total	32	100

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: It can be noted from the above table that 59.37% teachers are bearing excessive additional workload whereas 31.25% teachers are not in favour of the above statement. 9.38% teachers are not in position to say anything in this regard.

Table 6. Salary and incentive play important role in reducing occupational stress

S.N.	Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Yes	23	71.88
2.	No	9	28.12
	Total	32	100

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: A huge demarcation is shown from the above table that 71.88% teachers think salary and incentive have major role in reducing stress whereas only 28.12% of teaches don't support the above statement.

Table 7. Employer- Employee relationship in college

S.N.	Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Cooperative	13	40.62
2.	Exploitative (Underemployed)	16	50.00
3.	Can't say	3	9.38
	Total	32	100

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: Above table state that 40.62% teachers said that employers are cooperative and 50% the employer are exploitative whereas 9.38% teachers denied giving their answer in this regard.

Table 8. Employer behaviour and self respect of teachers is in poor state

S.N.	Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Agree	21	65.62
2.	Disagree	11	34.38
	Total	32	100

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: From the above table we can state that 65.62% teachers agreed the behaviour of employer is non cooperative and conservative and hurts the self respect of teachers whereas 34.38% have disagreed the above statement.

Table 9. Inadequate student's behaviour and negative attitude towards study

S.N.	Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Yes	19	59.37
2.	No	13	40.63
	Total	32	100

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: Above data reveal that 59.37% feels that student's behaviour is inadequate and negative towards study whereas 40.63% teachers contradict the above research statement.

Table 10. Regular physical exercise, yoga and meditation sessions will relieve the stress

S.N.	Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	To great extent	11	34.38
2.	To a certain extent	16	50.00
3.	Not at all	5	15.62
	Total	32	100

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: It can be stated with the help of above table that 34.38% teachers felt that regular physical exercise, yoga and meditation sessions helps to relieve the stress to a great extent, 50% teachers felt that regular physical exercise, yoga and meditation sessions helps to relieve the stress to a certain extent whereas 15.62% teachers are feels that the above does not help to relieve the stress.

Table 11. Due to occupational stress teachers are not able to enjoy their social and family life

S.N.	Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Agree	22	68.75
2.	Disagree	7	21.87
3.	Can't say	3	9.38
	Total	32	100

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: Above table shows that 68.75% teachers agreed that due to occupational stress teachers are not in position to enjoy their social and family life, 21.87% teachers denied the impact of occupation stress on social and family life whereas 9.38% have not given any answer in this regard.

Table 12. College has taken various measures to improve the Quality of Work Life of teachers and reduce the stress prevailing in them

S.N.	Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
3.	Yes	14	43.75
4.	No	15	46.87
5.	Can't say	3	9.38
	Total	32	100

Source: Primary data

Interpretation: Above data state that only 43.75% teachers are in favour that college has taken measures to improve QWL and reduce the stress prevailing in them whereas 46.87% teachers denied the above statement, 9.38% teachers have not given any clear response in this regard.

Findings

From the above data analysis, answers of open ended questions and personal observation the following findings have been put forth:

- ❖ Level of occupational stress in teachers of self finance colleges of urban area is less then teachers of rural areas colleges.
- ❖ Majority of male teachers are facing more occupational stress in comparison to female teachers, due to the lack of support system available to them and family responsibility that he has to meet in a very limited financial and other resource.
- ❖ It has been observed from the study that teachers of age group between 40 to 49 are in very high level stress due to high level of job insecurity and dissatisfaction whereas it is little less in the age group of 20 to 35 where the chance of career option (being permanent) decreases the effect of job insecurity and dissatisfaction.
- ❖ In comparison to joint family, teachers living in nuclear family are less in number due to various occupational stress factors such as low monthly income, job insecurity and poor opportunity for career development where as in joint family they get a level of physical as well as psychological support from other family members.
- ❖ Salary paid to teachers are mostly confined to ten to twenty thousand only and little less up to fifty percent are paid less than ten thousand which is bare minimum to improve their family life style and meet the monthly expenses. Salary structure is just like wage system as they are only paid for the days they worked. Salary payment is not even on time that leads to financial crises to teachers.
- ❖ Teachers are facing excessive additional workload in colleges and generally inferior type of academic and non-academic work has been taken from them. It leads to highly de-motivating factor and destruct their creativity to do work. Superior academic work is confined to permanent and regular faculties only.
- ❖ Employer's attitude is exploitative or underemployed towards the teachers; many of the time employers scold and shout on teachers in front of peoples and or in meetings which hurt their self respect and self esteem leading to cause a great level of occupational stress.
- ❖ It has been found that behaviour of rural students is more inadequate and negative towards study in comparison to the students of urban colleges. Such behaviour create hurdle in smooth functioning of daily class and cause occupational stress thereof.
- ❖ College organisational climate is not much growth centric in respect of teachers' career. They have very less opportunity for research, career planning and development. Due to temporary nature of employment, they are rarely permitted attend the orientation and refresher course, attend outstation conferences, delivering guest lecturer and participate in meetings and viva- voce of students. They are restricted to get

minor /major project and guiding Ph.D. scholar. Majorly they didn't get the study leave and have to resign the job for pursuing Ph.D.

- ❖ Majority of college does not take initiative to improve Quality of work life of teachers to reduce the stress prevailing in them. Even many of the times teachers are not given the legal holidays prescribed by the university. They are called even in holidays for work.
- ❖ Such occupational stress and psychological pressure affects the social and family life of teachers.

Recommendation

- Government should ensure the strict implementation of policies already made by the authorities such as higher education department, UGC and Ministry of HRD.
- 'Equal pay for equal work' order of Hon'ble Supreme Court has to be complied by the every educational institution and payment of salary should be on time.
- There should be organisation of get together function and make the growth full organizational climate in order to uplift the feelings and thoughts of the teachers leading to reduction in stress.
- College should involve the teachers in the top level meetings and consider their suggestion in management decision, this will lead to motivate the teachers and hence reduce the occupational stress.
- Government and college should jointly or separately organise various teachers' development courses, meditation, yoga courses and orientation/ refresher courses/ FDP for the teachers to magnify their personality, teaching aptitude and reduce their occupational stress thereof.
- There should be a proper career planning and development at college level that will reduce the job insecurity, dissatisfaction and occupational stress.
- The behaviour of the employer should be highly cooperative in making teachers the part of various research and academic activities of college.
- Teaching workload should be as per the UGC norms and other non-academic responsibilities/ workload should be dispersed in such a manner that it should not affect the social and personal life of the teachers.
- College should adopt all the measures on priority to improve the quality of work life of teachers.

Conclusion

This study has provided holistic information about occupational stress in the teachers of self- finance colleges of Varanasi District. Occupational stress at the workplace is major concern for all the teachers of self finance colleges. The study enlists that, the job insecurity, job dissatisfaction, absence of career planning and development is major cause of occupational stress. Majorly, the teachers are not supported for research and career development activities. Irregular salary disbursement and wage like salary structure is prevailing in the colleges which is enough low to meet the minimum requirement of personal and family need. The behaviour of employer-employee is critical and many of the time hurt the self- respect and moral of the teachers. In spite of that negative behaviour of students also found one of the cause of stress. It is found that up to certain extent regular physical exercise, yoga and meditation help in curing the stress level. Job stress affects the social and family life of the respondents. Few college of urban setting in comparison to rural colleges, have adopted the measures of QWL in proper way to strengthen the occupational health and made the organisational climate more responsive.

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